

Voronoi-Based Area Coverage Algorithms: Turning Real-World Fragility into Strength

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Abstract—The area coverage problem, where robots collectively monitor a region, arises in environmental monitoring, surveillance, and search-and-rescue. Centroidal Voronoi Tessellations (CVTs) offer a widely studied solution, partitioning space and positioning robots at cell centroids for optimal coverage. Existing work assumes perfect sensing and communication, or treats imperfections only as performance degraders. We take a different view: sensing inaccuracies and communication disruptions meaningfully shape system dynamics. Through rigorous analysis, we show that small position errors and Delaunay graph disruptions prevent convergence to static CVT equilibria, instead creating persistent dynamic behavior. This quantitative characterization reveals that sensitivity to imperfect conditions, often seen as fragility, can inspire new algorithmic strategies. Our findings challenge common theoretical assumptions and enable robust, adaptive multi-robot systems suited to unpredictable real-world environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Voronoi tessellation for a set of generators (e.g., a robot) on a bounded environment assigns cells of responsibility to each generator, where each point is assigned to its nearest generator. Centroidal Voronoi tessellations (CVTs) have the additional property that each generator lies at the centroid of its cell. The pioneering work [1] proved the optimality of CVTs for the area covering problem as measured by a large class of sensible, distance-based cost functions, and proposed decentralized gradient-descent control algorithms for converging to a CVT configuration. These results enable optimal sensor placement for networks of robots with access to local information only. Since then, CVTs underpin many coverage control strategies for autonomous robots. Extensions to dynamic environments, including adaptive control laws, were later developed in [2] and in [3] for disk-shaped robots with differing radii. Communication constraints are integrated into Voronoi-based coverage to balance spatial optimization with network connectivity in [4].

Collectively, these works highlight Voronoi tessellations and their adaptability to challenges such as mobility limits, connectivity trade-offs, and environmental complexity. All of them share a common distributed guidance law for individual robots, specifically a gradient-descent control law associated with a cost function whose minima correspond to positioning each robot at the *centroid of information* of its Voronoi partition. This approach typically requires a communication graph

containing the Delaunay graph, as in Figure 1. This condition implies that robots must sense neighbors sharing a common Voronoi cell boundary [5]. Related works [6]–[8] consider situations where robots perceive the same spatial point differently or have varying sensing radii. These discrepancies lead to inconsistencies in the construction of Voronoi cells, such as overlaps or gaps between neighboring cells. However, these studies typically maintain idealized assumptions, such as equal relative position measurements among robots and a globally consistent Delaunay graph for communication. In fact, some explicitly assume that robots can perfectly share consistent positional information [6]. Similarly, [9] addresses the effects of intermittent communication, modelled by a non-constant communication graph. Rather than quantitatively analyzing these *non-optimal situations*, these works primarily offer qualitative descriptions and focus on compensating for the associated imperfections, ultimately aiming to restore conditions close to the idealized scenarios for which the original algorithms were designed.

Our work considers the following: first, neighboring robots do not necessarily obtain equal measurements of their relative position, and second, no Delaunay graph is granted, modelling missing interactions between neighboring robots. Therefore, we pose three questions:

- To what extent is the area-coverage mission *reliable* when we assume that neighboring robots do not measure their relative positions equally?
- To what extent is the area-coverage mission *reliable* if a link in the Delaunay graph is broken, i.e. a critical communication fails?
- Can we benefit from such a non-reliability?

In this work, we provide formal answers to these questions for specific cases, which can be qualitatively generalized to more generic scenarios. Specifically, in the context of being *reliable*, we demonstrate the following effects once the mentioned imperfections are considered:

- Non-optimal coverage far from the desired one, even with only one missing link.
- Guaranteed collisions under specific topological or sensing failures.
- Unreachable static equilibria.
- Emergent behavior in the form of periodic trajectories.

The first two are somehow expected; however, the last two can be surprising. Nonetheless, this type of phenomena has already been reported in distributed formation control [10], [11], where gradient-descent control laws constructed from inconsistent relative robot states are shown to induce

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Fig. 1: On the left, Voronoi partition (solid lines) and its dual graph, the Delaunay triangulation (dashed lines). The robots are denoted by the red dots. Note that the Delaunay triangulation connects the robots whose Voronoi cells share a boundary. On the right, a directed 1-forest graph where, each node has only one outgoing edge.

non-designed collective motions. Robustness issues can be reframed as opportunities to harness emergent behaviors not originally intended. Indeed, to benefit from the latter two effects, e.g., by injecting these imperfections on purpose as in [12], we first need a thorough study of why they occur.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we introduce the employed notation and the necessary background on graphs and Voronoi partitions for the area coverage problem. We continue in Section III analyzing the area coverage problem under imperfect sensing and broken links where the robots are restricted to 1D parametrized trajectories [13]. In Section IV, we examine the area coverage problem when the map to cover is circular and the robots do not have any motion restrictions. Finally, Section V we concludes the paper and suggests directions for further research in the topic of area coverage with real deployments of robots.

II. PRELIMINARIES AND BACKGROUND

A. Graphs

A directed graph is a pair $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, where \mathcal{V} is a set with n elements called nodes and $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ is the edge set with pairs of nodes (u, v) called directed edges from u to v . A digraph is undirected if $(v, u) \in \mathcal{E}$ anytime $(u, v) \in \mathcal{E}$. For a given graph, u is an out-neighbour of v if there is a directed edge connecting v to u , i.e., $(v, u) \in \mathcal{E}$, and we denote by $\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}^+(v)$ the set of out-neighbours of v . Label the nodes with natural numbers and order the edges as $\{1, \dots, k, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|\}$, then from each k 'th edge (u, v) we construct the *incidence matrix* $B \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{V}| \times |\mathcal{E}|}$ of \mathcal{G} , whose $[B]_{ik}$ elements are $+1$ if $i = u$, -1 if $i = v$, or 0 otherwise. A *directed 1-forest graph* is a graph satisfying $|\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}^+(v)| = 1, \forall v \in \mathcal{V}$ (see an example in Figure 1), it will appear frequently in Section IV because of its mathematical convenience to model missing *Delaunay edges*; some graphs with cycles are 1-forest graphs, its incidence matrix B is square, and we will denote $v(i)$ the only out-neighbour of i .

B. Voronoi partitions and area coverage algorithm

Given a compact subset $\mathcal{W} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ and a set of points $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^2, i \in \mathcal{V}$, called *generators*, representing the positions of the nodes of a graph \mathcal{G} , its Voronoi partition is $V(p_1, \dots, p_n) = \{V_1, \dots, V_n\}$, where each V_i is the set of points that are closer to point p_i than any other point p_j with $j \neq i$, or more formally $V_i = \{q \in \mathcal{W} \mid \|q - p_i\| \leq \|q - p_j\|, \forall j \neq i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$ for each $i \in \mathcal{V}$. Each V_i is called a Voronoi cell. The interiors of the cells are disjoint and their union is \mathcal{W} so that it

is a partition, the boundary of each set represents points either at the boundary of \mathcal{W} or at equal distance to two or more generators, the latter are arbitrarily assigned to all cells. As shown in [14], the Delaunay triangulation $D(p_1, \dots, p_n)$, which is the geometric dual of the Voronoi diagram, provides the minimal required graph for computing the Voronoi cells, that is, the graph with fewer edges. This duality enables distributed computation since each robot only needs information from its Delaunay neighbours, i.e. neighbours in the Delaunay graph, to determine its Voronoi cell boundaries. Assuming an uniform distribution of information in \mathcal{W} , the optimal area coverage is obtained when the generators p_i are precisely at their Voronoi centroids [1], denoted by $C_{V_i} := \frac{1}{\int_{V_i} dq} \int_{V_i} q dq$, which is analogous to the center of mass of a region with uniform density. Assuming, as is customary, single-integrator dynamics for the robots $\dot{p}_i = u_i$, and the proportional error control law

$$u_i = -(p_i - C_{V_i}), \quad (1)$$

which is the gradient descent of a local cost function that measures the covered information of the cell, then the positions of all n robots will converge to a *centroidal Voronoi configuration* [1], meaning that at equilibrium robots are located at the centroid of their Voronoi cell.

C. Graph-constrained Voronoi diagrams under measurement imperfections

Many area coverage algorithms in their different flavors [1]–[3], [6]–[8] assume the Delaunay graph as the minimal granted interaction graph between the robots. However, such a condition can be challenged during real-world deployments which often face communication or sensing constraints; for example, when the density of robots is relatively high [15]. In fact, given an arbitrary communication graph \mathcal{G} , and a set of spatial points (generators) $P = \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$ let us define the *graph-constrained Voronoi diagram* $V(P, \mathcal{G}) = (V_1(P, \mathcal{G}), \dots, V_n(P, \mathcal{G}))$ of a compact set $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$

$$V_i(P, \mathcal{G}) := \{q \in \mathcal{W} \mid \|q - p_i\| \leq \|q - p_j\| \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}^+(i)\},$$

where $\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}^+(i) = \{j \in \mathcal{V} \mid (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}\}$ denotes the set of out-neighbours of node i , i.e. the nodes *seen* by i . We will see that it is common to witness an emergent behavior different from the designed one when \mathcal{G} has fewer edges than a Delaunay graph.

Regarding the imperfect measurements, we will consider that two neighboring robots i and j do not measure their relative position equally; more specifically we model systematic errors in the measurements as

$$(p_j - p_i)|_{\text{measurement}} = R_{ij} \left((p_j - p_i)|_{\text{actual relative position}} + \mu_{ij} \frac{p_j - p_i}{\|p_j - p_i\|} \right), \quad (2)$$

where we assume a bias in the range captured by a scaling factor $\mu_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}$ and in the direction, by a rotation matrix $R_{ij} \in SO(2)$. For example, due to some sensor calibration error. In general, we will consider that $\mu_{ij} \neq \mu_{ji}$ and $R_{ij} \neq$

TABLE I: Summary table of causes and effects in the area coverage mission with the 1D restricted motion for the robots.

Scenario		Behavior
Imperfect sensing	Open path	Equilibrium far from optimal
	Closed path	Circular motion
Interaction failure	Directed edge	Equilibrium far from optimal
	Undirected edge	Collisions

Fig. 2: The effects of the imperfect measurements and broken Delaunay graphs on more generic scenarios (left-hand side) where the motion of the robots is constrained can be studied by investigating a more mathematically tractable scenarios (right-hand side). In particular, we study the opened and closed 1D manifolds shared by all the robots. The blue dots are the robot positions whose motions are restricted to the 1D pink path, and the centroid (possibly with non uniform information density in \mathcal{W}), of the Voronoi cells are the red crosses with their projections on the path.

$R_{j,i}$. These imperfect measurements have an impact on how robots compute their own C_{V_i} in (1); for example, robots will not agree anymore on the boundaries separating their respective cells V_i .

III. AREA COVERAGE WITH CONSTRAINED 1D MOTION

In this Section, for the sake of conciseness and mathematical convenience, we will focus on robots with a common (open or closed) path to which their motions are restricted and where the domain \mathcal{W} must satisfy the property that each Voronoi cell has at most two neighboring cells as shown in Figure 2. Nonetheless, the consequences of imperfect sensing and broken Delaunay graphs could be extended seamlessly to more generic constrained scenarios as in [13].

Let us first consider as an example of open path, the interval (l_1, l_2) and order the labels of the robots so that $l_1 < p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_n < l_2$, where the positions $p_i, i \in \mathcal{V}$ represent their parametric coordinates along the curve. The centroidal Voronoi tessellation requires that the interaction graph contains the Delaunay graph, which in the 1D setting is a path graph, that is each robot $i = 2, \dots, n-1$ must sense at least its neighbours $(i-1)$ and $(i+1)$, whereas for the first and last robot the conditions are $\{2\} \subset N_G(1)$ and $\{n-1\} \subset N_G(n)$.

The one-dimensional case is analytically tractable with the graph structure encoded in the incidence matrix [16]. Voronoi cells are intervals bounded by midpoints $m_i = \frac{p_i + p_{i+1}}{2}$ between consecutive robots or endpoints l_1, l_2 , i.e., $V_1 = (l_1, m_1)$, $V_n = (m_{n-1}, l_2)$ and $V_i = (m_{i-1}, m_i)$ for $1 < i < n$. The centroids C_{V_i} are simply the midpoints:

$$C_{V_1} = \frac{1}{4}(2l_1 + p_1 + p_2), \quad C_{V_n} = \frac{1}{4}(p_{n-1} + p_n + 2l_2),$$

$$C_{V_i} = \frac{1}{4}(p_{i-1} + 2p_i + p_{i+1}) \quad \text{for } 2 \leq i < n. \quad (3)$$

Substituting the expressions for the centroids into (1), the system's evolution equations can be written compactly as a

linear system

$$\dot{p} = -(Ap - b), \quad (4)$$

where $b = (l_1/2, 0, \dots, 0, l_2/2)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and the matrix A encodes the interaction between robots

$$A = \frac{1}{4} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & -1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 2 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 2 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & -1 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}.$$

The stability of the linear system is determined by the eigenvalues of the matrix A . Since A is diagonally dominant and its determinant is non-zero (it can be proven that the determinant equals $\frac{n}{4^{n-1}}$), all eigenvalues of A are positive. This ensures that the system is stable, and the positions of the robots converge to a specific constant configuration p^* given by the solution to $Ap^* - b = 0$. It can be checked by direct substitution that the solution to this equations satisfies $p_i^* = l_1 - \frac{l_2 - l_1}{2n} + \frac{l_2 - l_1}{n}i$ for each robot. As predicted in [1], these solutions correspond to a centroidal Voronoi tessellation.

A. Imperfect sensing on open paths

When the robots measure imperfectly, it can be considered as a parametric disturbance of the exponentially stable autonomous system (4), and the equilibrium positions p_i^* just get shifted. Consider that robot $j \notin \{1, n\}$ has imperfect sensing as described in (2) so that the measured relative position $(p_j - p_{j+1})$ is biased by $\mu_{j,j+1} \neq 0$, and no angular bias is considered in the one-dimensional setting. This range bias distorts the computation of the centroid C_j in (3) so that robot j evolves according to (1) as $\dot{p}_j = -(p_j - C_j) = -\frac{1}{4}((p_j - p_{j-1}) + (p_j - p_{j+1} + \mu_{j,j+1}))$. Let $\tilde{b} = (0, 0, \dots, \mu_{j,j+1}/4, \dots, 0, 0)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^n$, then the autonomous dynamics of the system is $\dot{p} = -(Ap - b - \tilde{b})$. A superposition principle holds, so that the final equilibrium position is given by $p^* + \tilde{p}$, where p^* is the already found solution satisfying $Ap^* = b$ and \tilde{p} satisfies $A\tilde{p} = \tilde{b}$. The same superposition principle applies when more measurements are faulty. It is worth noting that \tilde{p} is always positive, that means that if one robot measures another further right than it really is, all robots will move to the right. Moreover, the distortion is the biggest at the faulty robot and decreases linearly with the difference, $|j - i|$, in the label of the robots j, i as $|j - i|$ increases. We then conclude with the following formal result.

Proposition 1. *Any biased range measurement shifts the equilibrium position of the autonomous system (4) in the direction of such a bias. All range biases contribute equality in superposition and their effects decrease linearly across the neighboring robots.*

B. Imperfect sensing on closed paths

When the robots are confined to a closed path, such as a circle, then it is known that following (1) the robots will converge to a configuration where they are equidistantly spaced [1], in fact the analysis is similar to (4) but with $A = BB^\top$ and $b = [-l/4, 0, \dots, 0, l/4]^\top$, where B is the incidence matrix of the ring graph and l the length of the

closed path. In this scenario, there is no preferred point in the 1D parametric space of the constrained path, so that the equilibrium position might alter by a common shift in the parametric position of robots, and the eventual positions of the robots in the circle are determined solely by their initial $p_i(0)$, this is due to the vector $\mathbf{1}_n = [1, \dots, 1]^T$ being in the kernel of A , an equidistant spacing arises due to the non-homogenous solution p^* to $Ap^* = b$. Moreover, as analyzed in subsection III-A, if only one robot is biased when measuring the relative 1D path parameter, then it *pushes* one neighboring robot in the same direction of the bias and *pulls* the other neighbor; thus, a collective motion emerges. This motion disrupts the original static equilibrium and drives the robots to move uniformly along the path, similar to the issues discussed in [11]. Note that the range biases will also distort the original equidistantly spaced equilibrium. We summarize the analysis with the following proposition.

Proposition 2. *Consider a system of n robots constrained on a closed path. If one robot is biased on the measurement of its relative parameter with respect to one neighbor, then there is no static equilibrium but a collective motion with constant velocity in the direction of the bias over the path.*

C. Communication-link failures

In general, for both open and closed paths, when a Delaunay link is removed between two consecutive robots, e.g., i and $i+1$, then, if a Delaunay triangulation is updated, then these two robots will share the same neighbors; namely $i-1$ and $i+2$. Consequently, by following the control law (1), robots i and $i+1$ will be attracted to the same spatial location, potentially crashing into each other. Alternatively, a situation in which robot i stops perceiving robot $i+1$, but not the other way around results in a distorted equilibrium position and therefore a sub-optimal area coverage; in particular, the eventual configuration can be far from the optimal one, e.g., for an open path, if $i = 1$ and does not perceive any other robot, then it will go the mid point of the 1D path, *squeezing* all the other robots in one the halves of the 1D path as illustrated in Figure 3. We distinguish between undirected and directed edge losses. In the former case, robots cannot see each other while in the latter only one robot can not see the other. We summarize with the following propositions.

Proposition 3. *Consider the area coverage problem driven with the autonomous system (4). If an undirected interaction is lost between two neighboring robots, then they will converge to the same equilibrium position.*

Proposition 4. *Consider the area coverage problem driven with the autonomous system (4). If one of the two directed interactions is lost between two neighboring robots, then the equilibrium position of all robots is distorted and can differ significantly from the desired optimal area coverage.*

Note that these two propositions, while apparently trivial, they can pose hard engineering problems when the number of considered robots is relatively high since these issues are more likely to happen, and there is no systematic method,

Fig. 3: Asymptotic behavior for 1D path-restricted robots, faulty robots and interactions are depicted in red color. At the top left, the prediction from Proposition 4: robot 1 squeezes the rest, resulting in a configuration far from the optimal area coverage. At the bottom left, the prediction from Proposition 3: robots 2 and 3 end up at the same location. At the right, the prediction from Proposition 2 with a closed path under measurement imperfections results in a circular motion. Two robots at their centroids but the faulty one measures its own centroid displaced from the actual one.

TABLE II: Summary table of causes and effects in the area coverage mission in 2D circular domain with a cyclic graph.

Scenario		Behavior
Cyclic graph	$n = \text{even}$	convergence (collinear equilibrium)
	$n = \text{odd}$	convergence (circular motion)
Cyclic graph & imperfections	$n = \text{even}$	non-existence of equilibrium
	$n = \text{odd}$	non-existence of equilibrium

so far, on how to mitigate such consequences while keeping a *suboptimal* area coverage.

IV. CIRCULAR AREA COVERAGE WITHOUT MOTION RESTRICTIONS

So far, the previously considered area coverage problem with restricted motion in one dimension and imperfect robots has been mathematically tractable. We now shift our focus to robots without motion constraints, considering a circular area to be covered to maintain tractability. To illustrate phenomena observed in non-Delaunay interaction graphs with fewer edges, we select the directed 1-forest graph. This topology enables a geometry-based analysis revealing the following: distortion from the optimal equilibrium solution, non-robustness against measurement errors such as those described in (2), and the existence of closed-orbit periodic solutions that may lead to unreachable static solutions. Though this graph constraint may initially appear far from a Delaunay graph, in some cases for the circular map the desired equilibrium with Delaunay only requires $|\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}^+(i)| = 2$ or a few more, whereas the directed 1-forest graph is just $|\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}^+(i)| = 1$; therefore, we are modelling some lost interactions in practice. Furthermore, the directed 1-forest graph allows us to derive closed-form expressions for centroid locations and an autonomous system dynamics model for robot positions. Crucially, the causes and explanations for the observed undesired behavior (based on first principles) remain consistent between the directed 1-forest graph and other graphs much closer to a generic Delaunay configuration.

A. Voronoi Centroids of One-forest Graphs

Let us define the domain \mathcal{W} as a circular compact set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ as in Figure 4, where we describe the position of the robots p_i with Cartesian coordinates whose origin is placed at the center of Ω . The Voronoi cells are described as $V_i = \mathcal{W} \cap H_i$, where H_i is the set that contains the point

Fig. 4: The position of two neighboring robots p_i and $p_{v(i)}$ in a directed 1-forest graph are denoted with triangles. For such an interaction topology, when \mathcal{W} is a circle, the related centroid C_{V_i} lies on a line through the center O , parallel to the relative position between neighboring robots.

p_i and is bounded by the perpendicular bisector n_i given by the segment between p_i and $p_{v(i)}$. These Voronoi cells are symmetric with respect to the line that is perpendicular to n_i and passes through the center of \mathcal{W} ; hence, the centroid C_{V_i} lies on this line. Note that the position vector from the center of the circle to C_{V_i} is parallel to the relative position vector between p_i and $p_{v(i)}$.

Precisely, the centroid of the cell can be expressed as

$$C_{V_i} = k_{iv(i)}(p_i - p_{v(i)}), \quad (5)$$

where

$$k_{iv(i)} = \frac{4 \sin^3\left(\frac{\theta_{iv(i)}}{2}\right)}{3(\theta_{iv(i)} - \sin(\theta_{iv(i)}))} \frac{1}{\|p_i - p_{v(i)}\|} \geq 0, \quad (6)$$

and $\theta_{iv(i)} \in [0, 2\pi)$ is the angle defined as $\theta_{iv(i)} = 2 \arccos\left(-\frac{\|p_{v(i)}\|^2 - \|p_i\|^2}{2\|p_{v(i)} - p_i\|}\right)$.

B. Closed-loop autonomous system

While a Delaunay graph gives Voronoi cells that are disjoint and cover the whole \mathcal{W} , for a directed 1-forest graph with $|\mathcal{N}_G^+(i)| = 1$ all the computed Voronoi cells overlap. Since for this scenario we have the expression for each C_{V_i} in (5), we plug it into (1), leading to

$$\dot{p}_i = u_i^c = -(p_i - k_{iv(i)}(p_i - p_{v(i)})). \quad (7)$$

If we stack all the control actions and define the stack vector of velocities $\dot{p} \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$, then we arrive to the following compact form

$$\dot{p} = ((I_n - KB^\top) \otimes I_2) p, \quad (8)$$

which is an autonomous system, where $p \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ is the stacked vector of robot positions, and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the incidence matrix of the directed 1-tree graph¹, $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is a diagonal matrix containing all the $K_{iv(i)}$ as in (6), and $I_n \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the identity matrix.

C. Emerging Coverage Behavior for One-Forest Graphs and Imperfect Measurements

Let us start with a result regarding the equilibrium configuration of the robots when all sensors are perfect but under the 1-forest graph.

Proposition 5. *Consider the autonomous system (8); then all possible equilibria correspond to a collinear configuration*

¹The expression $(B \otimes I_2)^\top p$ gives the relative positions in the graph.

Fig. 5: On the left, two robots in a squared area located at an equilibrium position since they have perfect measurements. The Voronoi cells and their centroids are depicted as perceived by the robots. On the right, robot 1 perceives robot 2's position with an angular measurement error, locating it at p'_2 . The corresponding Voronoi cell V'_1 and its centroid C'_1 are *distorted*, thereby disrupting the original equilibrium. In fact, this scenario leads to a rotational motion of the robots around the center of the area since the robots will start chasing their centroids without reaching them.

whose line passes through the center of \mathcal{W} , i.e., there exist scalars $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{R}$ and a unit vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that $p_i = \alpha_i v$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$ when $\dot{p} = 0$.

Proof. At equilibrium we have that $\dot{p}_i = 0, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}$, i.e., $p_i = k_{i,v(i)}(p_i - p_{v(i)}), \forall i \in \mathcal{V}$, which results in

$$p_i(1 - K_{i,v(i)}) = -k_{i,v(i)}p_{v(i)}. \quad (9)$$

Note that $k_{i,v(i)}$ is a scalar, then the condition (9) shows that for each robot i , the positions p_i and $p_{v(i)}$ are parallel. Since we have a directed 1-tree graph, we can conclude that all positions $p_i, i \in \mathcal{V}$ must be parallel to each other. Furthermore, since each p_i is a scalar multiple of $p_{v(i)}$, all robots must lie on a straight line passing through the origin. Therefore, there exists a unit vector v and scalars α_i such that $p_i = \alpha_i v$ for all $i \in \mathcal{V}$. ■

Proposition 5 shows that system (8) exhibits a fundamentally different behavior compared to the Delaunay graph. While the Delaunay-based algorithm naturally converge to configurations that optimizes area coverage [14], a different graph modelling missing interactions correspond to equilibrium configurations far from the desired one.

Let us continue by considering imperfect measurements in the relative positions between robots; for example, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Proposition 6. *Consider the autonomous system (8) but with the relative position between robots measured imperfectly as $(p_i - R_i p_{v(i)}), R_i \in SO(2)$; then no isolated equilibrium position can be reached by the system practically.*

Proof. The robot dynamics with the considered imperfect measurements are given by

$$\dot{p}_i = -(p_i - k_{i,v(i)}(p_i - R_i p_{v(i)})), \quad (10)$$

where for mathematical convenience we have represented the angular and the range measurement imperfections slightly different than in (2). The equilibrium condition $\dot{p}_i = 0$ is now $p_i = k_{i,v(i)}(p_i - R_i p_{v(i)})$, which implies, $p_i = \beta_i R_i p_{v(i)}$, for some $\beta_i \in \mathbb{R}$. Due to the cyclic nature of the 1-forest graph we can proceed recursively from p_1 to p_n to obtain the following condition for the equilibrium of (10)

$$p_1 = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n \beta_i\right) \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^n R_i\right) p_1. \quad (11)$$

Condition (11) implies that p_1 must be an eigenvector with corresponding eigenvalue 1 of the matrix $T := (\prod_{i=1}^n \beta_i) \cdot (\prod_{i=1}^n R_i)$; however, since the product of rotation matrices is itself a rotation matrix, T is a rotation composed with a scaling with factor $\prod_{i=1}^n \beta_i$ so that the condition can only hold if

$$\begin{cases} \prod_{i=1}^n \beta_i = 1, \\ \prod_{i=1}^n R_i = I_2 \end{cases}. \quad (12)$$

Note that as a subspace of all possible measurement errors, the condition (12) represents a zero-measure subset. Moreover, it is impossible to satisfy when only one robot has measurement errors. Therefore, system (8) with imperfections in the measurements of the relative positions cannot reach a static equilibrium in practice. ■

However, new types of emergent behaviour appears.

Proposition 7. *Consider the autonomous system (8) in a circular map of radius R with n robots. Let m be a divisor of n , then if robots occupy the vertices of a regular m -polygon centered at the origin and inscribed in a circle of radius $r = \frac{4}{3\pi}R \sin(\frac{\pi}{m})$ with periodic gaps between neighbours, then all robots stay in the circle moving at constant and equal speed.*

Proof. Firstly, we analyze how are the Voronoi regions corresponding to the proposed configuration. By symmetry, the perpendicular bisectors of adjacent vertices pass through the origin, therefore, Voronoi regions are half circles. We also know that the centroid of the cell lies on the line that is perpendicular to the perpendicular bisector and passes through the origin. Its distance from the origin can be obtain by calculating the integrals in the definition

$$C_{V_i} = \frac{1}{\int_{V_i} dq} \int_{V_i} q dq = \frac{\int_0^R x \sqrt{1-x^2} dx}{\int_0^R \sqrt{1-x^2} dx} \hat{x}_i = \frac{4}{3\pi} R \hat{x}_i,$$

where $\hat{x}_i = -\frac{(p_i - p_j)}{\|p_i - p_j\|}$ and R is the radius of the circular map. So, $\|C_{V_i}\| = \frac{4}{3\pi}R$ for all robots $i \in \mathcal{V}$. Secondly, the angle $\angle p_i o p_j$ is $\frac{2\pi}{m}$. Let X be a point in the perpendicular bisector so that $\angle p_i o X = \frac{1}{2} \angle p_i o p_j$. Moreover, $\angle p_i o X + \angle C_{V_i} o p_i = \frac{\pi}{2}$ since they are complementary angles. Thus, the angle $\alpha_i := \angle C_{V_i} o p_i = \frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\pi}{m}$ is independent of the robot i . Thirdly, note that from the statement we have $\|p_i\| = \frac{4}{3\pi}R \sin(\frac{\pi}{m})$, then $\|p_i\| = \|C_{V_i}\| \cos(\alpha_i) = r$ for all robots. Consequently, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \|p_i\|^2 &= p_i^\top \dot{p}_i = -(p_i^\top p_i - p_i^\top C_{V_i}) \\ &= -\|p_i\| (\|p_i\| - \|C_{V_i}\| \cos(\alpha_i)) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

so we can conclude that $\|p_i\| = r$ is invariant, so the robots stay in the initial circle. Lastly, note that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\dot{p}_i\| &= \|p_i - C_{V_i}\| \\ &= (\|p_i\|^2 + \|C_{V_i}\|^2 - 2\|p_i\|\|C_{V_i}\| \cos(\alpha_i)), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $\|p_i\|, \|C_{V_i}\|, \alpha_i$ are constant and equal for all robots. ■

Fig. 6: Robots start from a small area on the right side of \mathcal{W} . First and third images are the expected equilibrium for a Delaunay graph with undirected interactions. Each color is assigned to a Voronoi cell and its generator. Second and fourth images are from a cyclic interaction graph, a collinear stable configuration and an attractive collective motion respectively; only two Voronoi (overlapped) cells are shown for simplicity.

Fig. 7: Five robots in a polygonal domain. On the left, robots converge to the centroidal Voronoi tessellation equilibrium with a Delaunay graph. Secondly, red and blue robots lose interaction and converge to the same point. Thirdly, a cyclic graph induces periodic motion. Lastly, with a Delaunay graph, measurement errors between red and blue robots cause eventual chaotic but periodic motions for all the robots.

A particular case is obtained for n even and $m = 2$, then $\alpha_i = 0$, $\|C_{V_i}\| = \|p_i\|$ and $\|\dot{p}_i\| = 0$ for all i . That is, with even number of robots, a solution exists in which all robots do not move at all, with two clusters of $n/2$ robots that lie on the same point each.

Numerical simulations, see Figure 6, reveal distinct behavior depending on the parity of the number of robots. For an odd number of robots, the collinear equilibrium configuration is unstable, and when perturbed, the system converges to a stable periodic orbit. For an even number of robots, there exist at least two equilibrium configurations: one unstable periodic orbit, and one collinear stable configuration.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work has revealed fundamental fragilities in Voronoi-based coverage control algorithms under realistic imperfections, such as inconsistent measurements between neighboring robots and missing interactions in the required Delaunay graph. By analyzing diverse scenarios, we identified critical limitations: stable configurations deviating significantly from optimal coverage, persistent periodic emergent behavior, and even the inability to achieve static equilibria. Importantly, numerical experiments (see Figure 7) suggest these issues persist across broader conditions, highlighting their generality beyond the specific cases studied. These findings collectively challenge the standard assumption of perfect information exchange, which proves inadequate for real-world deployments where noise, delays, or communication dropouts are inevitable. To address these gaps, future work should prioritize robust control laws that preserve coverage quality under imperfect interactions. Furthermore, the observed periodic behavior—often a liability—could be repurposed as a feature, enabling purely reactive strategies for dynamic area coverage.

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